

Rationale for Code Commits Survey II

While performing various software development tasks (e.g., during code review), developers often need to answer "**why the code-change is this way?**" This is known as the **rationale of a code change/commit**. Finding the rationale of code changes is often hard. In this study, we would like to know about your experience with finding the rationale of code changes/commits.

Q1/3 Before you proceed to answer the following question, please take a moment to think of a **situation** in which you **investigated a code commit to understand its rationale** (why the code is this way?).

Write about one situation in which you investigated a code commit to understand its rationale.

Q2/3 Sometimes developers would give up their search for the rationale of code commits after some time. When do you **give up your search** for rationale of code changes?

Q3/3 Do you have **other thoughts/comments** about **searching for the rationale** for code commits?

Demographics Questions

Q1/5 How many **years** of experience do you have with **software development**?

Q2/5 Select all that apply, your **software development experience** is

- Personal
 - Professional (in a company)
 - Professional (open source)
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Q3/5 How many **years** of experience do you have with **version control systems** (eg. Git, Github)?

Q4/5 Select all that apply, your **experience** with **version control systems** is

- Personal
 - Professional (in a company)
 - Professional (open source)
-

Q5/5 What **version control systems** have you **used** for software development?

- CVS
 - Git
 - Mercurial
 - Perforce
 - Subversion
 - Other (please specify) _____
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Referral

Do you know anyone who would be interested in filling this survey? Please provide their contact information (name and email).

Are you interested in filling a followup survey? If yes, please provide your contact information (name and email).

Compensation

To be eligible for the Amazon.com gift card raffle, please enter your name and email address.

- Name _____
 - Email address _____
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